

LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING LARGE DEFLECTION THEORY

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic response of a graphite/epoxy laminated composite subjected to low-velocity impact is investigated using a finite element method based on the nonlinear theory. Dynamic von-Kármán plate equations considering large deflection are modified to include the effects of transverse shear deformations as in Mindlin plate theory. The rotary inertia effect is also considered. The Newmark constant-acceleration time integration algorithm is used in the finite element solution procedure. An experimentally established contact law through the statical indentation test is incorporated into the present finite element program. Numerical results, such as the contact force histories, deflection and dynamic strain in the plate, are presented.

INTRODUCTION

In low-velocity impact phenomena, large deflection of a plate occurs initially and locally at an impacted point. After impact, the local large deflection propagates to global deflection. Because of the initial and local large deflection, the small deflection theory may become inadequate and the large deflection theory must be used for an analysis of a thin laminated composite plate subjected to low-velocity impact. The nonlinear transient analysis of composite laminates using the large deflection theory is treated in a few references.^{1,2} In Ref.1 and 2, the transient response was investigated with given external forces.

This paper investigates dynamic large deflection response of a laminated composite plate impacted by a hard object. An experimentally established contact law³ is incorporated into the finite element program. The Newmark time integration algorithm is used to solve the dynamic finite element equations and Akay's constant coefficient scheme⁴ is used for an efficient iteration of nonlinear terms. The geometric boundary conditions of plate are simply supported or clamped.

VIRTUAL WORK OF LAMINATE AND INDENTATION LAW

Let the x - y plane coincides with the mid-plane of the plate with the z -axis oriented in the thickness direction. In the Mindlin plate theory, the displacement components of the plate are given by

$$\begin{aligned}u_1(x, y, z, t) &= u(x, y, t) + z\psi_x(x, y, t) \\u_2(x, y, z, t) &= v(x, y, t) + z\psi_y(x, y, t) \\u_3(x, y, z, t) &= w(x, y, t)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Here t is the time ; u_1 , u_2 , u_3 the displacements in the x -, y -, z -directions, respectively ; u , v , w the associated mid-plane displacements ; ψ_x and ψ_y are the rotations of the cross-sections perpendicular to the x - and y -axes, respectively.

By invoking the von-Kármán large deflection assumption, we have the Green-Lagrange strain-displacement relations. Using the laminate constitutive relations, we integrate the stresses and the stresses multiplied by z across the thickness of the plate.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_i \\ M_i \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{ij} & B_{ij} \\ B_{ij} & D_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_j^0 \\ \kappa_j \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} Q_2 \\ Q_1 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{44} & \bar{A}_{45} \\ \bar{A}_{45} & \bar{A}_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_4^0 \\ \epsilon_5^0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

or symbolically

$$\{\hat{\sigma}\} = [D]\{\hat{\epsilon}\} \quad (3)$$

In eqn.(2) and (3), N_i , M_i and Q_i are the in-plane stress resultants, the moment resultants and the shear stress resultants, respectively. A_{ij} , B_{ij} , D_{ij} and \bar{A}_{ij} are the respective in-plane, bending in-plane coupling, bending and thickness shear stiffnesses. $\{\epsilon_j^0\}$ and $\{\kappa_j\}$ are the strain and the curvature components, respectively.¹ To correct the shear effects in the z -direction, the analytical method by Whitney⁵ is applied to the computation of the shear correction coefficients.

Let us assume that the equilibrium configurations of the plate from time 0 to t have been obtained. Under the assumptions of the small strain and conservative loading, the virtual work equation of the plate subjected to dynamic load at time t is written as follows

$$\int_{S_0} \{\delta \hat{u}\}^T [\hat{\rho}] \{\ddot{\hat{u}}\} dS + \int_{S_0} \{\delta \hat{\epsilon}\}^T \{\hat{\sigma}\} dS - F \delta w_p = 0 \quad (4)$$

Here S_0 is the undeformed plate area; $\{\hat{u}\}^T$ the generalized displacements $\{u, v, w, \psi_x, \psi_y\}$; $[\hat{\rho}]$ the laminate mass matrix; w_p the plate deflection of the impact point, and F is the contact force between the plate and the impactor, which is determined by contact law given in Ref.3. The indentation, α , is given by

$$\alpha(t+\Delta t) = w_r(t+\Delta t) - w_p(t+\Delta t) \quad (5)$$

where w_r is the displacement of the impactor. The loading, unloading and reloading path have different contact law³.

FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION AND SOLUTION ALGORITHM

The finite element used here is the nine-nodal isoparametric quadrilateral element. The plate displacement field in the element can be expressed in terms of the nodal displacements.

$$\{\hat{u}\} = [\Phi] \{\Delta\} \quad (6)$$

where $[\Phi]$ contains the interpolation functions, and $\{\Delta\}$ is the nodal displacements vector. Substituting eqn.(6) and strain-displacement relations into eqn.(4), we can get the following finite element formulation.

$$[M]\{\Delta\} + [[K^L] + [K^N(\Delta)]]\{\Delta\} = \{F\} \quad (7)$$

where $[M]$, $[K^L]$ and $[K^N(\Delta)]$ are the mass matrix, linear stiffness matrix and nonlinear stiffness matrix of the laminate, respectively, and $\{F\}$ is the column vector containing the boundary and contact force.

The governing equation of the impactor assumed as a rigid body of the mass, m_r , is given by

$$m_r \ddot{w}_r + F = 0 \quad (8)$$

In order to obtain the solution of the impact problem, we must solve eqn.(7) and (8) simultaneously with the use of eqn.(5) and the indentation law. The Newmark constant-acceleration time integration method is used to solve eqn.(7) which is a nonlinear dynamic finite element equation. Also, the Akay's constant coefficient scheme is used for the efficient iteration of the nonlinear terms. With the use of the above two numerical algorithm, eqn.(7) can be written as

$$([K^L] + (4/\Delta t^2)[M])\{\Delta\}_{t+\Delta t}^{n+1} = \{F\}_{t+\Delta t} + [M]\{b\} - [K^N(\Delta)]_{t+\Delta t}^n \{\Delta\}_{t+\Delta t}^n$$

where

$$\{b\} = (4/\Delta t^2)\{\Delta\}_t + (4/\Delta t)\{\dot{\Delta}\}_t + \{\ddot{\Delta}\}_t \quad (9)$$

In the Akay's scheme, the nonlinear stiffness matrix can be considered as an additional equivalent force vector. In eqn.(9), successive iterations have to continue until the desired accuracy is obtained in each time step.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The laminated composite plate considered is 20-plyed $[0^\circ/45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ with dimension $15.24 \times 10.16 \times 0.269$ cm. The plate is assumed to be impacted at the center by an impactor with a diameter of 1.27cm, which can move only along z -axis. The boundary conditions are clamped or simply-supported with immovable conditions along all the edges of the plate. The indentation coefficients used here are given in Ref.3. The following elastic properties of a graphite/epoxy lamina has been used in this analysis.

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= 120 \text{ GPa}, E_2 = 7.9 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.30 \\ G_{12} &= G_{13} = 5.5 \text{ GPa}, G_{23} = 2.63 \text{ GPa} \\ \rho &= 1.58 \times 10^{-5} \text{ N} \cdot \text{s}^2/\text{cm}^4 \end{aligned}$$

In order to obtain numerical results, 4×6 finite element mesh has been used in one quadrant of the plate. The time increment is 2.5 μsec and total time analyzed is 800 μsec .

Fig.1 shows the comparison between the small and the large deflection theory for the contact force, central deflection and dynamic strain histories of the plate for the clamped boundary conditions. Fig.1(a) shows that there is no significant difference of the contact forces between two theories in the first contact duration. However, there is no third contact when the large deflection theory is used for this analysis. It is also interesting to note that the maximum value of the contact force during the second contact from the small deflection theory is larger than that from the large deflection theory. Fig.1(b) shows the time history of the dynamic strain at a point (1.43,0cm). The dynamic strains from the large deflection theory are greater than those from the small deflection theory in the first and the second contact duration. Fig.1(c) and (d) present the indentations which are the difference between the displacement of impactor and the deflection of plate, for the large deflection and for the small deflection theory, respectively.

Fig.2 shows the comparison between two theories for the contact force and dynamic strain histories of the plate for simply-supported boundary conditions. The contact forces from the large deflection theory are greater than those from the small deflection theory. Also, the dynamic strains from the nonlinear theory are estimated larger than those from the linear theory. Therefore, we may conclude that the response analysis for a thin laminated composite plate subjected to low-velocity impact requires the nonlinear analysis using the large deflection theory.

(a) Contact force history

(b) Dynamic strain on the bottom surface, ϵ_{xx} at a point (1.43, 0cm)

(c) Motions of the plate and the impactor for the nonlinear theory

(d) Motions of the plate and the impactor for the linear theory

Fig.1 Comparison of the results using the small deflection and the large deflection plate theory with an impactor having mass 27g and velocity 27m/s. (at clamped boundary condition)

The results of Fig.3 are obtained from the nonlinear analysis for the plate with clamped boundary conditions. Fig.3(a) and (b) show the effects of the velocity and the mass of the impactor, when the impactors have the same kinetic energy. The smaller mass of an impactor gives the shorter contact duration and more frequently variant dynamic strains. Also, the larger mass of an impactor results in the later occurrence of the maximum contact force. Fig.3(c) shows that the dynamic response frequency for a laminate subjected to low-velocity impact depends on only the mass of an impactor.

CONCLUSIONS

A finite element method based on a large deflection theory and transverse shear deformation has been used for the low-velocity impact analysis of a thin laminated composite plate. The linear theory underestimates the dynamic strain of the plate at a given point in this analysis, and overestimates the central deflection of the plate. The dynamic response frequency for a plate subjected to low-velocity impact depends on only the mass of an impactor.

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Fig.2 Comparison of the results using the small deflection and the large deflection plate theory with an impactor having mass 81g and velocity 9m/s. (at simply-supported boundary condition)

(a) Contact force history

(b) Dynamic strain on the bottom surface, ϵ_{xx} at a point (1.43,0cm)

(c) Central deflection of the plate

Fig.3 Nonlinear results with impactors having the constant kinetic energy or having the constant mass. (at clamped boundary condition)